

Introduction to Calculus and its application on the study of Movement, Alexandre Guiraud

William Fogg states that ‘The calculus is the greatest aid we have to the application of physical truth in the broadest sense of the word.’ Indeed, this powerful tool, whose foundations were manufactured by key physicians and mathematicians like Newton and Leibniz, has fundamentally helped with our human interpretation of physical movements.

Fundamentally, calculus is defined by the study of continuous change, just like geometry is designed to study shapes—whether they be as complex as a stellarator or as ‘simple’ as a square—calculus studies an infinite range of functions associated with key concepts like movement, interest rate, decomposition, etc.

The idea itself of calculus originates further back than we believe. Dating from 1820 BC, calculations of volumes and areas through integration can be found in the Egyptian Moscow papyrus. Yet the idea of a derivative and an integral originates from the 17th century, where the great minds of Leibniz and Newton defined the fundamental concepts of calculus. To this day, it has served as the cement to pave the way for numerous discoveries within the following years. Just 150 years ago, Gustave Eiffel used calculus to ensure the safety of the Eiffel Tower, evaluating the impact of wind on its structure.

Most of what you see around you is very likely to have been influenced by calculus, or a very close relative of this discipline; thereby, understanding the key pillars of calculus and its relationship with space and time is crucial to any aspiring engineers, architects, and anybody slightly curious about the functionality of what surrounds us.

This paper serves as a simple introduction to the application of calculus to physical movement or the global topic of kinematics. In order to understand this relationship, we’ll first look at a rough overview of what calculus is; of course, this paper won’t suffice to fully grasp the full concept of the discipline but will serve as an accessible entry to the topic. For the sake of coherence, we will respect the following outline:

- Explanation of key concepts 1 : scalar and vector quantities
 - Scalar and Vector
 - Distance and Displacement
 - Speed and Velocity
- Explanation of key concepts 2 : derivation and integration
 - Derivatives
 - Integration
 - Fundamental theorem of calculus
- Application of calculus : Position and displacement
 - Position, displacement and velocity
 - Velocity and acceleration
 - Solving key equations
- Conclusion

Explanation of key concepts 1 : scalar and vector quantities

§1: Scalar and Vector

The concepts of scalar and vector quantities are key when attempting to study the nature of movement. Being able to characterize the quantity you are calculating is essential in not only achieving a concrete result but globally understanding how kinematics operate. Now one must be able to clearly outline the difference between the two types of physical quantities in order to proceed with attempting to solve any kinematic equation. The first type of physical quantity is a scalar quantity. Most physicians would define a scalar quantity as something that has an identifiable magnitude. For instance, a car that has traveled 100 meters in 20 seconds would have a speed of $5 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. This value only takes into account the magnitude of this movement; thereby, speed is a scalar quantity. Contrastingly, the second physical quantity is a vector quantity, which possesses a magnitude as well as direction. If we take the same car and make it drive for 200 m East and then 400 m West over the span of 50 seconds, its velocity will be equal to $4 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ West. In our second example, this car not only has a magnitude but a direction as well. Therefore, we can conclude that velocity is a vector quantity. We can dress the following table in order to recognize that quantities are scalar and vector:

Scalar Quantities	Vector Quantities
Distance (eg : 450 m)	Displacement (eg : 20 m North)
Speed (eg : 100 m/s)	Velocity (eg : 34 m/s South)
Mass (eg : 40 kg)	Acceleration (5.20 m/s^2 West)

Furthermore, we can attempt to further understand the differences between the scalar quantity of distance and the vector quantity of displacement within a 2-dimensional scale. In order to understand how both of these quantities function, we consider the following scenario:

§2: Distance and displacement

A man walks from point A to point B, then turns around to walk over to point C. The distance between points A and B is equal to 15 meters, and the distance between points B and C is equal to 40 meters. What would the distance be equal to as opposed to the displacement?

In order to calculate the total distance travelled by this man, you would add the distance between AB and the distance between BC. This would lead to arriving at a total distance of $40 + 15 = 55$ meters traveled. Contrastingly, in order to find the displacement of this man, we would have to look at his initial position and where he ends up. In order to be clear and concise in this reasoning, we will associate negative integers with the west and positive integers with the east. Therefore, the man travels $+15$ meters east and -40 meters west. We then find that his global displacement is $15 - 40 = -25$ meters west. A displacement can be positive or negative, but it must be associated with a certain direction and magnitude.

Now, if we were in a 3-dimensional space, this whole line of reasoning would still work, but this is when the use of vectors will become key. For the sake of conciseness, we won't cover distance and displacement on a 3D scale.

§3: Speed and Velocity

We can now focus on the difference between speed and velocity. As mentioned prior, speed only has a magnitude, whereas velocity has a magnitude and a direction. For instance, you wouldn't say a car is going at a speed of 30 m/s south since it is in fact going at a velocity of 30 m/s . Most people will recognize the formula to calculate the total speed of an object, known most commonly under the letters: where d corresponds to distance and t to time. In contrast, the value of the total velocity is equal to $v = d'/t$, where v corresponds to the velocity, d' to the displacement, and t to the time. Our displacement can be either positive or negative; hence, so can our total velocity. If we look at a similar diagram as prior, we can observe the key differences between velocity and speed:

A man walks from point A to point B, then turns around to walk over to point C. The distance between points A and B is equal to 15 meters, and the distance between points B and

C is equal to 40 meters. This whole journey took him a total time of 35 seconds. What would the total speed be equal to as opposed to the total velocity?

If we start with our total speed, we can observe that the total distance traveled was, as calculated prior, 55 meters. As well, the time interval given is equal to 35 seconds, enabling us to use our formula to find its speed: $s = 55/35 = 1.57 \text{ m/s}$.

Constrastingly, if we were to find its velocity, we would use the total displacement, which was originally equal to -25 meters. Therefore, its velocity is equal to $v = -25/35 = -0.71 \text{ m/s}$.

From this information, we can calculate the instantaneous velocity of an object. In order to find such a value, we would have to use the concept of limits. Indeed, the instantaneous velocity corresponds to the limit of the difference in time as it tends to 0: $v = \lim(\Delta t \rightarrow 0) d/t$. This whole concept might seem tricky at first, but the following chapter will elucidate any questions as we will cover the key pillars of calculus and how we can use them to find our instantaneous velocity and other values.

Explanation of key concepts 2 : derivation and integration

§1: Derivatives

In order to understand the complex study of movement, one must first have some understanding of key concepts like derivation, integration, and calculus overall. The study of calculus and its various applications can be simply explained as the study of change. For instance, we write V the volume of a balloon. We assume this balloon to be a sphere, therefore its volume being equal to $\frac{4}{3}\pi \times r^3$, with r being equal to its radius. Now let's say we slowly deflate the balloon, allowing air out and thereby inciting some form of change where both my volume and radius start decreasing. One might then wonder how these quantities relate to one another and how we can form a model to understand their relationship. In order to find the answer to this question and solutions to any problem relating to change, we would have to use calculus and its key principles.

The first key branch of calculus is the idea of derivatives. This concept, founded by Newton and Leibniz, allows us to find the instantaneous value of a function. If you're reading this, you are most likely already familiar with the idea of the slope of a function, also known as the rise over run, which serves as a description of the rate of change of a vertical variable (found on the y axis) with respect to a horizontal variable (found on the x axis). The common method to find the slope of a function is by comparing two points on your given function. Take the following linear function, for instance :

We are given two points that lie within the graphical representation of this function without any other information about its slope. How would we find the overall change of this function? In order to answer this question, you would have to analyze its leading coefficient. To do such a task, you'd compare the change in x with the change in y. Let's go back to our original function. Between point A with coordinates (2,0) and point B with coordinates (4,4), there is a change in x equal to $\Delta x = x_b - x_a$ which equates to $4-2=2$. As for the change in y, it is equal to $\Delta y = y_b - y_a = 4$. Finally, we look at the relationship between these two values by calculating their ratio. Therefore, the slope of our function is equal to $\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} = 4/2 = 2$.

Now this seems simple enough; in fact, it is taught to children as young as 12, but how would we find the rate of change of such a function knowing that the relationship between the y variable and the x variable was always varying? Consider the function $f(x) = y = x^2$, unlike our previous linear function, where the rate of change was constant, meaning that any two points had a proportional relationship. We will not find the global rate of change, but the instantaneous rate of change using derivatives. Here is our previously mentioned function :

How would we be able to find the given derivative at point (1,1)? If we were to find the slope of this function using the same formula used for a linear function for points (0,0) and points (1,1) as well as point (1,1) and point (2,4), we'd find something similar to this:

Whilst this doesn't give us information about the rate of change of this function, it does indicate the fact that each series of points found on it is not proportional to one another. If we were to now ask ourselves a more interesting question, one where we attempt to find the instantaneous change of a certain point, we would be a step closer to derivatives. Using the function x^2 , if we were to look at the instantaneous change when x is equal to 1 at point A, we could draw a line, or a tangent line, which corresponds to the slope of the function when $x = 1$. This would not only give us a graphical representation of this change but also give us an actual value that corresponds to this change. In order to achieve this tangent line, we know we need two points because a line is a geometric construction that links two points, no matter their distance. The issue faced is that when we link two points on our previous function, we reach no apparent accurate rate of change due to the fact that the evolution is not

proportional. Now let's say we were to introduce a new point, a point B, one whose x coordinates are very similar to point A, say $x = 1.1$. Our slope would then again be equal $\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x}$, in our case, 2.1, giving us a slope similar to the following:

This is a decently accurate rate of change; as shown graphically, our tangent line seems to be somewhat correct, but we can make it more precise. As mentioned prior, the slope of a line is found through the formula $\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x}$, or in our case $\frac{y_b - y_a}{x_b - x_a}$. If we were to make the distance between point A and point B as small as possible, we would have the most accurate rate of change. In other words, when our change in x tends to 0, we would find our instantaneous rate of change, also known as the derivative. Let's translate this idea into our original formula :

$\Delta y = y_b - y_a$ where we introduce the variable h, representing the distance between A and B, and representing our x value, therefore $y_b = f(a + h)$ and $y_a = f(a)$ so $\Delta y = f(a + h) - f(a)$.

As for the change in x, also known as h, it will tend to 0. Therefore, we can rewrite our expression as $f'(x) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(a+h) - f(a)}{h}$, with $f'(x)$ corresponding to the derivative of our original function. Let's go back to our initial problem and find the derivative of x^2 at any given point x. We simply use the previous formula and simply input our values :

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x+h) - f(x)}{h} \Leftrightarrow \frac{(x+h)^2 - x^2}{h} \Leftrightarrow \frac{x^2 + 2xh + h^2 - x^2}{h} \Leftrightarrow \frac{2xh + h^2}{h} \Leftrightarrow \frac{h(2x+h)}{h} \Leftrightarrow 2x + h$$

As h tends to 0 through our use of limits, the derivative of x^2 approaches the value of 2x, giving us our derivative.

Now that we have established the slope, we can identify the tangent line associated with a given point. For the sake of simplicity, we will simply look over the formula and an

application rather than the mathematical proof. The equation of a tangent line y at any given point a is found using the following formula :

$$y = f'(a)(x - a) + f(a)$$

We have finally obtained all the tools we need to find the instantaneous rate of change of our function in our previous point A. Not only can we find its derivative, but its tangent. You can yourself try to find the equation of a tangent when $x = 1$.

In order to find the solution to this problem, we first find the derivative :

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(1+h)-f(1)}{h} \Leftrightarrow \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{1+2h+h^2-1}{h} \Leftrightarrow \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} 2 + h \Leftrightarrow 2$$

Now we can apply the formula of a tangent to find its equation :

$$y = f'(1)(x - 1) + f(1) \Leftrightarrow 2(x - 1) + 1 \Leftrightarrow 2x - 1$$

By observing the relationship between the tangent and the curve, we understand that the equation of the tangent found is in fact correct. In addition, we can summarize key identities when it comes to deriving a function in the following table:

Function	Derivative
a	0
x	1
ax	a
x²	2x
xⁿ	nxⁿ⁻¹
$\frac{1}{x}$	$-\frac{1}{x^2}$
\sqrt{x}	$\frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}}$

A key concept that we need in order to proceed with the rest of this introduction is the mean value theorem. The mean value theorem states that if a function $f(x)$ is continuous on a

closed interval $[a,b]$ and differentiable on the open interval (a,b) , then there exists a point c in (a,b) where

$$f'(c) = \frac{f(b)-f(a)}{b-a}$$

This means that at some point c , the instantaneous rate of change, also known as the derivative, equals the average rate of change over $[a,b]$. Geometrically, there is at least one point where the tangent to the curve is parallel to the secant line connecting a with $f(a)$ and b with $f(b)$.

§2: Integrals

While derivatives enable us to find the instantaneous gradient of any point on any slope (given its domain), this is not enough to complete somewhat of our understanding about calculus and the global study of movement. The second key pillar of calculus focuses rather upon finding the area under a curve, also known as an integral. One might wonder why we find such a value; after all, we have always regarded functions as one-dimensional geometric constructions rather than two-dimensional shapes. Indeed, the area under a curve, relative to the given function, represents the total value of the function over a given interval. Mathematically, this is often expressed through the concept of integration. Common uses of this area are, for example, when calculating the total energy in a system, the consumer surplus and, in our case, finding values to represent the displacement, velocity, and acceleration of an object. In order to start thinking about a method to achieve this value, let's imagine any possible method for us to calculate the area under a curve. Similarly to derivatives, we can lean on relatively simple mathematical concepts to fuel our understanding. Imagine you were calculating the area of the shape down below. In order to find the total area, you would separate this shape into different rectangles, leading you to an interpretable value, where we find A_1 by adding A_2 and A_3 :

Let's now translate this into the graph of a curve. If we were to simply replace the area under our curve with rectangles of different sizes according to its relationship with the function, we'd get an inaccurate idea of the area, but at least a start to approaching a precise value. Using the distance between a point a and a point b , we could approximate the area by replacing it with a vague replacement of such through rectangles. Thus, translating it into a graph would give us something similar to the following :

We'll call n the number of rectangles we introduce to calculate the area under the curve in between a and b , in our case 4. The area of any rectangle at a point Δx_1 would then be $A_{\Delta x_i} = \Delta x_i \times f(\Delta x_i)$, since we multiply the width equal to Δx_i times the height, equal to $f(\Delta x_i)$. Thus, adding the area of each of these rectangles would give us an approximate idea of the area under our given curve. We note that the more rectangles we include and the smaller their individual width becomes, the more precise our answer is. The way we'd write this in mathematical notation would be the sum of the area, giving

$$\sum_{i=1}^n f(x_i) \times \Delta x_i$$

We quickly realize that our result is limited as we associate n with a finite number, and when calculating the area, it will simply give us a rough approximation. In order to find the precise result, we would have to make n tend to infinity and Δx_i to 0. Now we can use the concept of limits in order to find our best possible result. we rewrite our expression to a clearer notation and its eventual most common notation :

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^n f(x_i) \times \Delta x_i = \int_a^b f(x) \times dx$$

This unpolished formula is roughly the concept of integration and the method to figure out the area under a curve. Now, all of these formulas are strictly theoretical and don't help us in any way to find any actual result, leading us to use the idea of derivatives to figure out an answer. In order to go further, let's sketch a new function :

In this graph, the x axis corresponds to time, and y represents the speed of an object noted $s(t)$. The area of any rectangle would be, $\Delta t \times v$ which is equal to distance as we multiply seconds by meters per second. So the area under the curve corresponds to the total distance between point 0 and point T, referring to a variable that gives us an insight as to what our distance interval is, meaning that :

$$d(T) = \int_0^T v(t) \times dt$$

Now we can ask ourselves, what is the derivative of $d(T)$? First of all, a tiny change in distance over a tiny change in time is equal to our instantaneous velocity, its exact definition. This means that $\frac{ds}{dT}(T) = v(T)$. Going back to our graph, if we were to make a slight nudge to the right, it would cause the area under the curve to increase by a certain amount, noted ds and represented by a rectangle. The height of this rectangle is the height of the graph at this certain point, also known as $v(T)$, the width of the rectangle, which is noted dT . We can rewrite our expression, which is an approximation of how much the area has increased, as :

$$ds = v(T) \times d(T) \text{ or } \frac{ds}{d(T)} = v(T)$$

This mathematical demonstration lets us know that the derivative of any function giving us the area under a curve is equal to the function of the curve itself. Whilst it may seem tricky, the way you should look at our problem now is what function has a derivative equal to $v(T)$. In other words, if our original function were to look something like $v(t) = -t^2 + 5t$, what function, when derived, would it give us $-t^2 + 5t$?

We can start by noting $V(t)$ the antiderivative $v(t)$, meaning that $V'(t) = v(t)$. Now we know from the previous chapter that the derivative of x^a is equal to ax^{a-1} . With this knowledge, we can conclude that $V(t)$:

$$V(t) = -\frac{t^3}{3} + \frac{5t^2}{2} + c$$

There is one simple issue with this line of reasoning, being the fact that any constant, when derived, is canceled out. Meaning that in all technicality there is an infinite number of possible combinations of $V(t)$ that all equal $v(t)$ when derived. In order to find this missing constant noted c , we focus on a piece of information we have yet to use : the lower bound of our integral. In the previous example, the lower bound was equal to 0, and it was shown that the function passes through the point (0,2). This would mean that when $t = 0$, $V(0) = 2$, in other words, our constant c is equal to 2, giving us a definite integral. The process used is applicable in any other case of integration.

§3 : Fundamental theorem of calculus

Now that you are somewhat acquainted with the ideas of integrals and derivatives, we can begin to study the fundamental theorem of calculus. This theorem enables us to understand the complete relation between derivatives and integrals and completes this introductory section to calculus. Understanding it is essential to understanding the study of movement. Here we will not only prove it in more depth but also demonstrate other key properties of integrals and calculus overall.

The first part of this theorem is being able to find a notation to represent the link between derivatives and integrals. As mentioned briefly earlier, the derivative of an integrated function is equal to its original function, meaning that derivatives are opposite calculations of integration. We'd write it as such :

$$F'(x) = f(x)$$

We have slightly proven this in the previous chapter, using the analogy of velocity time and distance, yet we have not fully uncovered the full mathematical explanation as to why we can draw such a conclusion. Here we will go through a step-by-step detailed analysis to prove the first part of the fundamental theorem of calculus. We associate $f(t)$ with a

continuous function during the interval $[a;b]$ as well as $F(x) = \int_a^x f(x)dx$, where $x \in [a; b]$,

in other words $a \leq x \leq b$. The following graph can be associated with this given function :

In order to prove this theorem, we first try to find the derivative of $F(x)$, also known as $F'(x)$, which using the basic formula of derivatives gives us something along the lines of :

$$F'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{F(x+\Delta x) - F(x)}{\Delta x} = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\int_a^{x+\Delta x} f(x) dx - \int_a^x f(x) dx}{\Delta x}$$

Now, if we were to look at our graph and compare the area under the curve of x and $x + \Delta x$, also written as $\int_a^{x+\Delta x} f(x) dx - \int_a^x f(x) dx$, we see that this expression can be

rewritten as $\int_x^{x+\Delta x} f(t) dt$. This means that we can rewrite $F'(x)$ as :

$$F'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\int_x^{x+\Delta x} f(x) dx}{\Delta x} = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\Delta x} \times \int_x^{x+\Delta x} f(x) dx$$

And using the knowledge of the mean value of definite integrals, we know there exists a c where $x \leq c \leq x + \Delta x$. We can add this to our graph, giving us the following :

This indicates that $f(c) \times \Delta x = \int_x^{x+\Delta x} f(x)dx$, or in other words, the area of the curve is equal to $f(c) \times \Delta x$. We can simplify this function by dividing both sides by Δx , giving us $f(c) = \frac{1}{\Delta x} \times \int_x^{x+\Delta x} f(t)dt$. Using our previous expression, we can determine that there exists a value $c \in [x; x+\Delta x]$, showing that the derivative of our integrated function is equal to the limit of $f(c)$:

$$F'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} f(c)$$

So really the question being asked here is what the value of $f(c)$ is as Δx approaches 0. We already know that $c \in [x; x+\Delta x]$, or in other words $x \leq c \leq x + \Delta x$, indicating that as c approaches x , Δx will tend to 0. This would also mean that as $f(c)$ approaches, $f(x)$ it Δx tends to 0. Meaning that intuitively we can rewrite our expression as :

$$F'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} f(c) = f(x)$$

This indicates to us that integrals and derivatives work in opposite ways, or, in other words, deriving a function and later integrating it will result in finding the same initial function :

Now, evaluating $F(x)$ at a and b , we get $F(b)$ the accumulated area from 0 to b , which $F(a)$ represents the accumulated area from 0 to a .

We can rewrite both of the areas $F(a)$ and $F(b)$ the subtraction of one from another as :

$$F(a) = \int_0^a f(x) dx$$

$$F(b) = \int_0^b f(x) dx$$

$$F(b) - F(a) = \int_0^a f(x) dx - \int_0^b f(x) dx$$

Subtracting these values, we find that $F(b) - F(a)$ gives the total area under $f(x)$ from a to b , which, using the property of definite integrals, we can rewrite as :

$$F(b) - F(a) = \int_a^b f(x) dx$$

To sum up this final part of our introduction to calculus, you mostly need to remember the formula just above this text alongside the explanation as to why integrals and derivatives work opposites to one another.

Application of calculus : Position and displacement

§1 : Position, displacement and velocity

Now that we have the basic knowledge needed about derivation and integration, we can begin focusing on studying the nature of movement, in other words, the displacement, velocity or acceleration of a particle. On the one hand, we'll focus on position and displacement in order to have a gradual understanding of this topic rather than diving directly into more complex notions like the relation between velocity and acceleration.

In textbooks, we usually associate the function $s(t)$ with the position function and the variable t with time. As seen prior, we can use this position function to not only find the distance traveled by a particle but also its displacement. We would write displacement as the difference between the coordinates of the final position and the initial position :

$$\text{displacement} = s(b) - s(a).$$

We have also established how to find the net velocity of a particle, which would be equal to the net displacement divided by the difference in time : $v = \frac{s(b)-s(a)}{b-a}$. This works because we are essentially doing the average velocity between the two points a and b.

We can focus on position, displacement and velocity. We know that position is the value associated with the location of the object with respect to time. Now, displacement is the difference in the object's position from one time to another, and velocity is defined as the rate at which an object changes its position also with respect to time. Finally, instantaneous velocity can be considered the average velocity; only the average you are taking into account needs to be on the smallest scale possible. This leads us to wonder : what does the instantaneous rate of change of the position of a particle correspond to ?

Let's break it down using derivatives. Using our knowledge of derivatives, we know that finding the gradient of a point on a function indicates the instantaneous rate of change. We also understood that in order to find the best approximation, we would have to find points that would need to tend to one another; in other words, their distance should approach 0. We can use our basic formula learned during the introduction to calculus. In our case, we are using the function for position $s(t)$, so to approach an instantaneous value of $s(t)$, we would use the exact same formula, where we attempt to find the slope between the points a and b when the distance between one another becomes as small as possible :

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow b} \frac{s(b)-s(a)}{b-a}$$

As a tends to b, b-a tends to 0, as both values would be equal to each other; therefore, we will have reached the smallest scale possible to find the instantaneous rate of change of our position function. But we remember having defined the instantaneous velocity previously as the net displacement between two points over their difference in time on the smallest scale imaginable. So we can conclude that when we derive our position function, we find the instantaneous rate of change, also known as the instantaneous velocity :

$$s'(t) = v(t)$$

While this whole concept might seem slightly blurry, let's analyze an actual example for you to better understand. We are given the function $s(t) = -t^3 + 6t^2 + 9t - 10$ defined on the interval $[0;6]$ and are looking for the instantaneous velocity at point $t = 3$. We have already explained that in order to find a more accurate value for the instantaneous velocity, we'd have to narrow down the margin between points a and b. Since we are focusing on the value $t = 3$, we can use values for a and b equal to 2.9 and 3.1. Notice how these values together keep the same average as the one we are focusing on. So let's calculate this :

$$\frac{s(3.1)-s(2.9)}{0.2} = 17.99$$

This approximate value is already quite precise, yet using our definition of derivative, we know we can identify the most accurate result. Indeed, if we were to use values for a and b that are as close to one another as possible, we'd find a more and more correct result. We could do this by using the values $a = 2.999999$ and $b = 3.000001$, but this would be too complicated of a process for something that can be done in a much more efficient and elegant manner. In fact, we can use our prior knowledge about calculus to help us identify this instantaneous value for velocity. In order to do such, we calculate the derivative of $s(t)$ and then plug in our desired value $t = 3$:

$$s'(t) = -3t^2 + 12t + 9 \qquad s'(3) = -27 + 36 + 9 = 18$$

The value found for $s'(3)$ is then equal to the rate of change at point $t = 3$, or in other words, our instantaneous velocity, which here is equal to 18 meters per second in some direction. The only issue with this answer is that we have not identified in which direction our particle is going. Velocity is a vector quantity, meaning that it has a magnitude alongside a direction, yet how do we find such direction? Well, for the sake of cohesion, we associate positive values for velocity with a movement directed to the right and negative values with a movement directed to the left. When the velocity is zero, or when there is an inflexion or turning point on the curve $s(t)$, our particle is then either at rest or changing direction.

One final step we can add to complete our understanding of velocity and position is the fact that integrals and derivatives work as opposites. This indicates that when we derive a certain function, integrating it will lead us to its original value, given sufficient information. So when we say the derivative of position is velocity, we must also mean that the integral of velocity is position. Really, we can rewrite our expression of $s(t)$:

$$s(t) = \int v(t)dt$$

If you were in a scenario where you were to use integration when studying movement, remember that all key rules still apply. For example, remembering if your integral is definite

or not. Usually, if a question required you to integrate velocity, you would be given a certain value for $s(x)$ in order to find the correct definite integral. Therefore, from this chapter we have concluded that not only is the derivative of position velocity, but also this can indicate the direction of our particle.

Velocity	Direction
Positive $v(x) > 0$	Going towards the right
Negative $v(x) < 0$	Going towards the left
Equal to zero $v(x) = 0$	Particle at rest or changing direction

§2 : Velocity and acceleration

Acceleration is a vector quantity that we can define as the rate of change of velocity per unit of time. In other words, acceleration is the instantaneous rate of change of velocity at a given instant relative to a point, as shown below. By now this should ring a bell in your head, as this is once again the definition of derivatives. It's important to note that just like position and velocity, you can go back and forth through derivation and integration between acceleration and velocity, given that you respect the key rules of integrals. Instead of focusing once again on proving why one equals the derivative of another and how by integrating acceleration we find velocity, let's rather study what the sign of our velocity and acceleration can tell us about our particle.

$$a(t) = v'(t)$$

$$v(t) = \int a(t)dt$$

On one hand, what can you tell me about the velocity of an object when its acceleration is positive? Well, for one, we know that acceleration is velocity's derivative, meaning that if the acceleration is positive, then the tangent to the curve has a positive gradient, meaning that at that instant, the function of velocity is increasing. Using the same logic, we can as well conclude that when acceleration is negative, velocity is decreasing. Finally, when the acceleration is equal to zero, this indicates that the velocity is constant, and so is its speed.

Positive acceleration	Velocity is increasing
Acceleration equal to 0	Velocity is constant
Negative acceleration	Velocity is decreasing

Using our values for acceleration and velocity, we can also determine whether our particle is speeding up or slowing down. In the first case, our velocity and acceleration have the same sign, either positive or negative, indicating that we are speeding up. Now, on the flip side, if our velocity and acceleration have different signs, our particle is speeding down.

Particle is speeding up	Acceleration and velocity have the same sign
Particle is slowing down	Acceleration and velocity have different signs

The final key step to understanding the relationship between velocity and acceleration is by studying the direction of a particle relative to the values of velocity and a neutral acceleration.

Let's go through, case by case, different possible scenarios for the value of velocity and acceleration. In the first scenario, our velocity is positive and the acceleration is equal to zero, which means that logically we are going to the right due to the positive velocity and that our speed is constant because our acceleration is null. Furthermore, when our velocity and acceleration are both equal to zero, we can conclude that not only is our particle staying at rest, but it is also at a constant speed. Thirdly, if our velocity is equal to zero but our acceleration is positive, we can not only find out that the particle is at rest due to the neutral velocity but also that it is about to move to the right because its acceleration is positive. We also add that the particle speed is increasing. Finally, if the velocity is equal to zero and its acceleration is negative, we use the opposite reasoning and conclude that our particle is about to move to the left. All of this can easily be summed up in the following table :

Velocity	Acceleration	Direction	Speed	Velocity
Positive	Equal to zero (0)	Right	Constant	Constant
Equal to zero	Equal to zero (0)	Staying at rest	Constant	Constant
Equal to zero	Positive	At rest and about to move to the right	Increasing	Increasing
Equal to zero	Negative	At rest and about to move to the left	Increasing	Decreasing

§3 : Problem solving

Now that you have been given all the tools needed for the study of movement, we can shift our focus to a real-life example to concretize this lesson :

The author of this introduction, Alexandre Guiraud, is paragliding in the Alps. He starts off at Rochebrune and lands at St. Nicolas after a total time of 1 minute and 40 seconds. During his journey, the direction of the author as well as his speed vary. The author is interested in finding his acceleration and direction after 40 seconds, as well as his position after 80.

Thankfully, we have managed to find the velocity of his movement during his flight, which we associate with the function $v(t) = \frac{-t^2}{10} + 10t + 5$. For the sake of comprehension, a positive direction will be associated with movement towards the East, and a negative direction will be associated with movement towards the West. As well, we have been provided with a singular value of his position, $s(0) = 10$. Can you help the author ?

Answer :

Step 1 : Summarizing

We can first start by summarizing the data that has been offered to us. We are informed that the function for velocity $v(t) = \frac{-t^2}{10} + 10t + 5$, as well as a singular value for his position, $s(0) = 10$. In this exercise, we have to analyze the acceleration of the author at a given time t_1 as well as his position at a time t_2 .

Step 2 : Acceleration

Using our previous information, we know that by deriving velocity, we can find the value for the acceleration of a particle, or in our case, the paraglider. We then find :

$$a(t) = v'(t) = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{-t^2}{10} + 10t + 5 \right) = -\frac{t}{5} + 10$$

Now to find the acceleration at a point $t = 40$, we simply input such a value in our acceleration function, giving us : $a(40) = -\frac{40}{5} + 10 = 2$

So we have now figured out that the acceleration of the author after a time of 40 seconds is equal to $2 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$. Now the problem also asks us to give the direction of the paraglider at this exact time. We know that the acceleration after 40 seconds is positive, and from that $v(40) > 0$, we can determine that the author is moving in a positive direction, or, in other words, to the East.

Step 3 : Position

We have also learned that by integrating the velocity of a particle, we can find its exact position, given that we are provided with a singular value of our position function. Giving us:

$$s(t) = \int v(t)dt = -\frac{t^3}{30} + 5t^2 + 5t + C$$

Thankfully, we have been provided with a value for position and know that the position of the author after 0 seconds is equal to 10. Therefore, we can find C in the following manner :

$$s(0) = -\frac{0^3}{30} + 5(0)^2 + 5(0) + C = 10$$

$$C = 10$$

$$s(t) = -\frac{t^3}{30} + 5t^2 + 5t + 10$$

Finally, we can find the value for the position of the author after 80 seconds by solving $s(80)$, which is equal to the following :

$$s(80) = -\frac{80^3}{30} + 5(80)^2 + 5(80) + 10 = 15743.33$$

We convert this value to kilometers, giving us a total displacement of 15.7 kilometers traveled after 80 seconds.

Step 4 : Conclusion

The author has an acceleration of $2 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$ after 40 seconds, which we associate with a movement directed towards the east. As for his position, we have concluded that he has traveled 15.7 kilometers after 80 seconds.

Hopefully you have now understood the key pillars of calculus and are comfortable with applying them to real-life situations in order to study the movement of a particle. If you have any further questions, contact me and I'll try my best to guide you towards your desired answer. Here is my email address: a.guiraud26@jmanuel.org.uk